

IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROBLEM AND MANAGEMENT ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC RESULTS OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

Onysko S.,

Lviv National University of Nature Management, Ukraine

Lyzak M.

Lviv National University of Nature Management, Ukraine

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Abstract

On the basis of an expert survey of managers and specialists of agricultural enterprises of the Lviv region of Ukraine, the following characteristics were determined: quality of planning of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises; measures of formation of the organizational and management subsystem of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises; the state of the institutional and regulatory basis of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of the enterprises of the industry; efficiency of production and technological activity of agricultural enterprises; level of work motivation at agricultural enterprises; the rationality of the analytical and monitoring apparatus of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of the activities of enterprises of the industry; measures of realization of the economic and resource potential of agricultural business entities; problematic aspects (restrictions) of income formation and final financial and economic results of agricultural enterprise management; availability of processes of extended reproduction and sustainable business development at agricultural enterprises. On the basis of the obtained results, conclusions were drawn regarding the problematic aspects and obstacles of managing the financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises in the region.

Keywords: *agriculture, enterprises, financial and economic results, efficiency management, mechanism of formation of results.*

In the context of implementing the policy of improving the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results, it is important not only to summarize the relevant key parameters and performance indicators of agricultural enterprises, but also to identify problematic aspects in terms of organization and management in this area. Since we are talking about problems in the part of management, it is possible to identify the degree of realization of the potential, as well as obstacles to achieving the planned financial and economic results of enterprises, using the tools of sociological research.

Therefore, the analysis of the quality of management of these processes acquires special relevance and importance in relation to the formation and further implementation of an effective policy of agricultural enterprises to improve their financial and economic results. That is why the study of the quality of management of the processes of forming the financial and economic results of the management of agricultural enterprises was carried out by means of an expert survey (questionnaire of managers and specialists of enterprises in the Lviv region of Ukraine), which was conducted in the fall of 2021 at the analyzed agricultural enterprises.

3 persons from each of the analyzed enterprises, who are managers or leading specialists of structural subdivisions, were involved in the expert study. Thus, a total of 21 people were interviewed.

Methodologically, the questionnaire consisted of 10 questions, the answers to which together allowed to obtain information regarding the following 5 aspects:

1) measures of implementation of basic management functions (planning, organization, motivation, control) in the field of management of financial and

economic results of agricultural enterprises (2 questions);

2) the quality of the activities of agricultural enterprises in relation to the construction and functioning of structural and functional subsystems of the formation of financial and economic results (4 questions);

3) the level of realization of the economic and resource potential of business entities in order to achieve appropriate financial and economic results (1 question);

4) underutilized opportunities (shortcomings) to ensure income, as well as profit and profitability of economic entities (2 questions);

5) the state of ensuring reproductive processes, achieving sustainable development of enterprises (1 question).

The most important and even integral aspect of the quality management of business processes is the implementation of the planning function. Planning allows you to outline in advance both the totality and the sequence of measures that need to be implemented to achieve the set goal and objectives. On the other hand, planning involves determining the quantitative parameters of functioning, the achievement of which, in fact, signals the realization of the corresponding goal and tasks, and, on the contrary, deviation from these results will be evidence of non-fulfillment of the set plans. Accordingly, with the use of planning, the ability of the enterprise to optimally allocate available resources and potential to achieve financial and economic interests is achieved. When it comes to financial and economic results, the importance of planning is further strengthened mainly from the position that the results of financial and economic activity are, in fact, the final end point of the operating cycle, and, therefore, are determined by the consequences of the entire spectrum of events from the

moment of the first and to the last iteration in the entity's business processes. Without proper planning, there are no grounds for concluding that the enterprise has quality management of financial and economic results.

Despite this, only 14.3% of respondents gave an affirmative answer that plans for the financial and economic state / development of the enterprise are being developed on an ongoing basis at the enterprises they represent. At the same time, another 9.5% noted that such planning is not carried out at the enterprise.

It is obvious that in the conditions of the complicated business environment, the objectively existing crisis and external obstacles caused first by COVID-19, and later by the war, a significant number of enterprises have personnel limitations, especially in specialists not related to production activities, and carry out management processes of production and financial and economic activity to a large extent intuitively. However, this cannot serve as an acceptable reason for the low level of planning of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises. In our opinion, there is a rather acute problem in improving this management function within the mechanism of forming the financial and economic results of enterprises, including the introduction of modern methods of forecasting, modeling and programming of various scenarios of behavior, changes in the situation and their consequences for the financial and economic results of management.

Although it is positive that, for example, 33.3% of analyzed enterprises practice periodic forecasting of key financial and economic indicators, and 23.8% financial and economic planning is carried out at the preparatory stage of the implementation of new business projects (related to investments) and/or starting new lines of business.

In our opinion, the results of the respondents' answers to the question regarding the formation of the mechanism of formation of their financial and economic results in the enterprises of the organizational-management subsystem can be considered to be largely favorable. The complete absence of such a subsystem was declared by 9.7% of the respondents, and in the general structure of all answers, this option scored only 4.2%.

For some reason, other options for answers that characterize certain aspects of the specified subsystem of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises turned out to be sufficiently "scattered", which may or may not be evidence of a complete understanding of the essence of individual elements of the subsystem, the existence of the fact of their existence, or the non-building of their structure within a single complex with interconnected elements. Thus, the majority (38.9% in the overall structure and 71.4% within this answer option) believe that the organizational and management subsystem in the field of ensuring the financial and economic results of enterprises is embedded in the general system of business management, which is both positive and No. The reverse argument may refer to a certain substitution of concepts and the desire to hide highly specialized management in this area within the general management system.

Certain confirmation of such a conclusion can be served by the lack of clear delegation of the organization's function (only 9.3% in the overall structure and 19.1% within this answer option), as well as the presence of an almost even distribution of answers among three key aspects of the organizational and management subsystem – management of business activity (13.4% and 28.6%, respectively), budgeting of production and economic activity (16.3% and 33.3%) and management of financial and economic results within the general organizational and management system of management (20.9% and 42.9%).

In our opinion, there are no critical problems with the organizational and management subsystem at agricultural enterprises. However, there is a need to implement more modern practices of organization and management, their focus around the final financial and economic results of management in order to ensure economic security, competitiveness and sustainable business development.

At the same time, we notice a slightly worse situation in terms of the state of the institutional and regulatory basis of the mechanism for forming the financial and economic results of the analyzed agricultural enterprises. Because, in general, this problem is characteristic not only of financial and economic results, but of management in general, and not only for agricultural, but for most domestic enterprises in most branches of the national economy. We are talking about a low level of standardization of management as a set of requirements, rules, instructions and principles for the implementation of reference measures and actions at business entities in relation to business management as a whole, and in this case - ensuring proper (including planned) financial and economic results management. The institutional and regulatory basis of the mechanism for the formation of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises is a set of relations between the subjects of the internal and external environment using communication tools, mechanisms and means of managing processes in the analyzed sphere. Therefore, its institutionalization requires a significant amount of work in the field of standardization of quality management. But at present, there is still no sufficient corporate understanding of the importance of such changes, which may also be due to a lack of appropriate resource (mainly financial) support.

From the answers of the respondents, we can state at the moment only separate manifestations of the construction of the institutional and regulatory basis in the analyzed field at agricultural enterprises. Accordingly, it is positive that 18.8% of the analyzed enterprises have already implemented procedural regulations for the development of business processes, 15.6% have clearly defined the parameters of the formal and informal institutional business environment, and 6.3% have developed and implemented normative and legal regulation of financial management economic results. However, activities in this direction are still not sufficient, and enterprises should work on improving the institutional and regulatory basis of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of management. This is despite the fact that within the relevant

options, 19.1% of respondents affirmatively answered that institutional and regulatory support at enterprises has not been implemented. The specific weight of this option is also high in the overall structure of experts' answers - 12.4%.

In our opinion, the introduction (institutionalization) of a full-fledged institutional and regulatory basis for the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results will contribute to better management of the processes of production and technological activity efficiency. This conclusion is based on the fact that, at present, in the situation of a low level of standardization of the quality of business management, agricultural enterprises still manage to guarantee a relatively high level of efficiency of production and technological processes. Thus, 71.4% of respondents believe that the level of efficiency of production and technological activity of enterprises of this type of economic activity corresponds to the average level of the industry (in the overall structure of answers, this option gained about a third - 29.4%).

14.4% of managers and specialists of enterprises spoke of low efficiency in this area, and 28.6% of respondents said that it was lower than the industry average. The corresponding indicators in the general structure of answers were 5.8% and 11.8%. As we can state, in general, the efficiency of production and technological activity of a fairly large part of agricultural enterprises is still low, and this is a negative factor in the context of the formation of proper financial and economic results of management.

On the other hand, some positive manifestations are also present. These are, for example, the formation of a rational industry-production structure at enterprises (57.1% of respondents believe so; in the general structure, this answer option was 23.5%), the completeness of the measure of logistical support of enterprises (42.9% and 17.7% respectively), adequate supply of material and technical base and use of innovative technologies by business entities (28.6% and 11.8%).

Thus, there are reasons to assert about the significant reserves of agricultural enterprises in relation to the further efficiency of their production and technological activities, the implementation of which has direct positive consequences in terms of increasing the amount of profit and increasing the level of business profitability, improving other characteristics of the financial and economic results of management.

This can be greatly facilitated by increasing the level of labor productivity, one of the leading factors of which is a high level of its motivation. Currently, according to the results of the expert survey, this management function is implemented only partially and more than half consists exclusively of remuneration (this answer option was 28.1%) and the material component of motivation (23.4%), as well as to a greater extent applies to management personnel of enterprises (18.8%).

Confirmation of insufficient rationality and quality of work motivation systems at agricultural enterprises is also the fact that only a small part of the respondents defines its condition as high (9.4%). The imbalance of the work motivation system is evidenced by the low level of its distribution to the workforce (only

9.4% of responses), as well as the limitation of non-material staff stimulation practices (10.9%).

Stimulating work is considered one of the key factors of increasing efficiency and prerequisites for improving the financial and economic results of organizations in modern management. Therefore, it is very important for the management of agricultural enterprises to improve their activities in this direction. Moreover, the priority should be the formation of a work motivation system with a balanced set of elements, tools and means, a mandatory connection of the level of remuneration and non-material incentives in accordance with the obtained final business results.

Despite motivation, the basic and integral function of management is the function of control, the proper application of which solves a number of tasks at once: first, tracking whether all processes are taking place as planned; secondly, observing the temporal characteristics of the course of changes; thirdly, observation of the absence of deviations in the quantitative values of key parameters and indicators of volumes and efficiency of management, their consequences for the financial and economic condition, security processes and reproduction of capital and assets of business entities; fourthly, the formation of conclusions regarding the implementation of the goal and the achievement of the financial and economic interests of enterprises.

In this context, it is positive that 9 out of 10 (90.5% in the structure of respondents' answers to this question) enterprises have established monitoring of financial and economic activity. This indicator is also high in the general structure of respondents' answers - 37.3%.

Periodic tracking (and also on a permanent basis) of the values of indicators of financial and economic activity, including financial and economic results, is evidence of high attention to control of the relevant processes. However, such work is still not systematic, which is negative. 11.8% of respondents stated that the enterprise has implemented a permanent system of research into the financial and economic status and business results, and at the same time operational control of key indicators is carried out (in the structure of answers to this question, the indicator was 28.6%).

At the same time, the values of the answers were high (80.9% within the answer option and 38.3% in the general structure), that the corresponding analysis is carried out within the general system of analyzing the financial and economic activity (state) of the enterprise at the end of the analyzed period (mostly - calendar year). And this is positive. However, it does not meet the modern realities of competitiveness and security. In particular, enterprises to a very limited extent develop and implement their own (taking into account the branch and specifics of the organization and business) methods and techniques (5.9% in the general structure and 14.3% within the response option); apply modeling of the influence of alternative options of management decisions on the financial and economic results of management (3.9% and 9.5%, respectively).

Even more negatively, in our opinion, it is necessary to consider the presence of manifestations of a complete lack of implementation of the function of analysis and control of financial and economic results

at agricultural enterprises. Currently, this is typical for every fifth answer (19.1% within the relevant option) and for 7.8% of enterprises in general. Therefore, there is a need to improve the analytical and monitoring apparatus of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises. At the same time, the key vector should be the creation of an ongoing system of analysis and control with preliminary modeling of the consequences of internal and external trends, ongoing monitoring of the course of processes and their consequences, periodic comprehensive analysis of financial and economic results and factors of their formation with the use of modern effective methods of analysis and diagnostics.

At agricultural enterprises, the connections between the elements of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of management are still not formed and are currently characterized by a certain diversity, which does not correspond to leading foreign practices. We can assert this by comparing, for example, the results of evaluating the efficiency of production and technological activity and the degree of realization of the economic and resource potential of agricultural enterprises. The obtained values testify in favor of the predominance of the second characteristic. In particular, 34.2% of the interviewed experts believed that the realization of the economic and resource potential of enterprises is at an above average level, and another 26.3% claimed that it is at an average level.

Respondents' answers related to the low degree of realization of the economic and resource potential were relatively low, namely 2.6% indicated that the level of realization was low and 10.5% - below average.

However, here too there is potential for further improvement. Thus, there is a certain dissonance between the mentioned high results and, for example, the fact that only 7.9% of experts indicated that the economic and resource potential of the business is fully realized. In addition, there are characteristic differences in the levels of implementation of the managerial and resource components of the potential, currently in favor of the managerial one (13.2% versus 5.3%). However, the very fact of recognition of differentiation is rather negative and is evidence of the existence of problems both in terms of effective use of resources (production, material and technical, technological, personnel, etc.), and in terms of full realization of management potential.

These arguments provide grounds for concluding that there is an urgent need for better management of the processes of formation and realization of the economic and resource potential of agricultural enterprises, as well as taking into account the relevant processes both during the justification of policy provisions and the assessment of the degree of its implementation in relation to the achievement of high values of financial and economic results management.

As noted in the theoretical and methodological part of the study, financial and economic results go beyond the purely final results of management, which are profit and profitability, and are determined by parameters of safety and competitiveness, increase of own cap-

ital, trends towards expanded reproduction and sustainable development, etc. However, in any situation, at the initial stage, everything is determined primarily by the volume (production and sales) of economic activity, which ultimately forms the income of enterprises. Income maximization is a direct way (with an effective cost management policy) to the growth of the final business results. Therefore, it is important to identify which components are characteristic of certain obstacles and restrictions for enterprises in terms of increasing income.

The results of the expert survey made it possible to state that these are mainly problems in the field of the material and technical base, first of all its availability and level of modernization (80.9% within this answer option and 17.2% in the general structure of the problems of increasing the income of enterprises), production economic infrastructure, the state of its development and modernity (61.9% and 13.1%, respectively), yield and efficiency, as well as price policy (52.4% and 11.1% respectively) of agricultural enterprises.

At the same time, the problem of the quality of production and marketing activity (42.9% and 9.1% respectively) of the enterprises of the industry remained sufficiently high. A much lower level of problems was characteristic of the quality of the used raw materials and planting material (2.0% in the overall structure and 9.5% directly according to this component of income formation), the development of the logistics system (23.8% and 5.0%), security of enterprises by sowing areas / production and economic premises, the available assortment structure of agricultural products (33.3% and 7.1% respectively).

Therefore, the obtained results provide grounds for asserting that the increase in the amount of income of agricultural enterprises is closely correlated to a significant extent with the modernization of the material and technical and technological base of production, the development of the production and economic infrastructure, as well as the improvement of the marketing system of enterprises, its evolution in accordance to modern progressive trends, including the formation and development of Internet marketing systems and digital marketing communications.

For the most part, production factors also determine the level of profitability and profitability of agricultural enterprises, which is logical when the industry belongs to the real sector of the national economy with a high content of cost-intensive management. Thus, 61.9% of experts pointed to the production cost as one of the key factors in the formation of profit (profitability) (in the overall structure of answers, the indicator was 21.0%).

Accordingly, the value of the impact on profitability of such a factor as the management of the total costs of enterprises also became quite high (42.9% within this answer option and 14.5% in general). Thus, only the production cost and general costs of enterprises by about 35% serve as limitations (obstacles) to further increase in the level of profitability of agricultural business. At the level of cost management, managers and specialists of agricultural enterprises determined the

importance of the "Liquidity" factor. Obviously, this can be due to the difficulties of quickly selling products and making calculations in conditions of critically high external instability. Instead, its storage and maintenance leads to increased costs and, accordingly, a decrease in profitability.

At the same time, a fairly large part of the interviewed experts considers the probability of further growth in the profitability of the existing agricultural business to be a sufficiently pessimistic scenario (including from the standpoint of high cost-intensiveness) and as a way out of the situation points to the need to diversify activities (including horizontal) in order to receiving additional income from other sources. This opinion was held by 57.1% of enterprise representatives, and this answer took the second position in the overall structure, reaching a value of 19.4%.

On the other hand, as the results of the analysis showed, such factors as business activity, financial stability and asset management affect the profitability of agricultural enterprises, but to a somewhat lesser extent. Yes, everything is equal, a total of about 30%.

Fig. 1. Results of experts' assessment of the availability of extended reproduction and sustainable business development processes at agricultural enterprises, 2021.

Note: only 1 answer option

Source: compiled based on the results of an expert survey

For representatives of another 9.5% of business entities, stable functioning and full system coverage of expenses is characteristic. Thus, every second enterprise, in fact, successfully implements the processes of its extended reproduction, which is positive. At the same time, none of the interviewed experts indicated the answer option that enterprises are characterized by stable unprofitability.

It is important to maintain these trends, but a number of business entities are not so stable. The option "There is a small amount of debt from previous periods" is still typical for 19.1% of representatives of agricultural enterprises, "There are periods of boom and bust" - for 23.8%. Another 4.8% of enterprises function not so much due to income and profit as due to the accumulation of external liabilities. Thus, achieving stability in sustainable functioning and development, expanded reproduction (as the most systemic characteristics of the best financial and economic

Therefore, in order to ensure further growth of profitability, it is important for the management of enterprises to form a system of tools, the implementation of which will generally ensure this, but with a higher level of attention to resource and energy saving, the introduction of more productive (in particular ICT) technologies, vertical and horizontal diversification (including the creation of diversified corporate structures), acceleration and efficiency of business processes.

Measures in the specified areas have a direct positive impact not only on the growth of profits and the increase in the level of profitability, but also closely correlate with the provision of better prerequisites for expanded reproduction and sustainable development of agricultural enterprises. However, they are already sufficiently typical for the subjects of this industry, when 42.9% of experts consider the development of enterprises to be stable, at the same time, against the background of an increase in the volume of economic activity, assets and the number of employees of enterprises (Fig. 1).

results of management) are still relevant issues for domestic agricultural enterprises. Moreover, to achieve this goal, it is expedient to direct the entire set of measures in all other directions of the policy of improving the financial and economic results of business.

CONCLUSIONS.

With the application of the expert survey method, problematic aspects of the elements of the mechanism of formation of financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises were revealed. This is mainly due to: lack of practices of careful planning of final generalizing indicators of production and financial and economic activity, processes of structural changes in capital, liabilities, safety parameters, competitiveness, extended reproduction of enterprises; the existence of a need for institutionalization of the institutional and regulatory basis and modernization of the

organizational and management subsystem of management in the analyzed area; insufficiently high efficiency of production and technological activity, implementation of economic and resource potential, reproduction and sustainable development of agricultural enterprises and the imbalance of the system of motivation of the work of their personnel, its untargetedness and weak connection with the achievement of the planned values of the parameters of the financial and economic condition and efficiency; limited practices of modeling the impact of management decisions (their alternatives) on the final results of management, the use of modern, including our own, methods of assessment and diagnosis of financial and economic results of management;

there is a high need (in view of the realization of the potential for increasing income and increasing the profitability of business) in the modernization of the material and technical and technical and technological base, the production and economic infrastructure of enterprises, the problems of productivity and quality of production, as well as the marketing, especially price, policy of enterprises, their management costs and processes of vertical-horizontal diversification. The effective policy of improving the financial and economic results of agricultural enterprises should be primarily directed to the elimination of these shortcomings.

References:

1. Andrusenko, H. O. (2003). Strategy of state regulation of the agrarian sphere of agroindustrial complex. Actual problems of public administration. Vol. 2, pp. 9-14.
2. Bondarevs'ka, K. V. (2014). The problem of price disparity and ways to solve it in the field of agriculture. *Biznes Inform.* Vol. 8, pp. 129-133.
3. Vasylytsy, T. G., Urazaliyev, R. M. (2011). Generalization of enterprise economic security conceptual basis. *Scientific Bulletin of NLTU of Ukraine.* Vol. 21.2. pp. 153-158.
4. Vasylytsy, T. G., Yaroshko O. R. (2011). Financial safety of enterprise: place in the system of economic security and priorities of strengthening on the post-crisis stag of development of economy. *Scientific Bulletin of NLTU of Ukraine.* Vol. 21.2. pp. 132-136.
5. Hmyria, V. P. (2016). State support for financing agricultural production in Ukraine. *Economics and enterprise management.* Vol. 3, no. 23, available at: <http://fp.cibs.ubs.edu.ua> (Accessed 21 January 2022).
6. Dovzhyk, O. O. (2016). State regulatory agricultural policy in the context of world experience. *Economy and society.* Vol. 2, pp. 97-102.
7. Lupak, R. L., Didych, A. M. (2010). Economic bases of providing of competitiveness of enterprise in the conditions of market relations. *Scientific Bulletin of NLTU of Ukraine.* Vol. 20.6. pp. 248-252.
8. Panukhnyk, O. V. (2017). State support of agricultural entities. *Actual problems of innovative economy.* Vol. 1, pp. 5-10.
9. Horovetska, Y. (2017). *Agriculture in Ukraine: Economic and Political Frameworks*, Research Division Eastern Europe and Eurasia, Berlin, Germany.
10. Shtets T., Lupak R., Vasylytsy T. General aspects of state policy for the digital transformation of the national economy. *International independent scientific journal.* 2020. № 20. Vol. 20. 14-19.